

Co-creating the UK SKA Regional Centre (UKSRC): Social & economic impact focus group discussions

Three focus groups were organised as part of a series of activities which enabled the UK community to participate in the co-creation of the proposal for the STFC's funding call '[UK Square Kilometre Array \(SKA\) Regional Centre: 2022](#)'.

Key points overarching points.

- UKSRC will change its activities from being a mainly engineering focused project in the next three years, to one that is enabling data analysis for astronomers. Socio-economic impact can be created across all phases. Our activities need to be targeted and tailored to the appropriate stage of the project.
- There is a lot of enthusiasm for the UKSRC and SKA across the community. The project could improve coordination, lower the barrier and enable people across the UK to contribute to creation of impact from the SKA project.
- There is a lot of ongoing activity in SKA, wider astronomy community and digital research infrastructures. The aim is not to duplicate activities. The UKSRC project could focus on enhancing and adding value to existing activities. The project's impact activities should focus on our strengths and develop partnerships with others where appropriate.
- UK Square Kilometre Array (SKA) is a long term project. This is the first three years of this activity; the project should focus on developing processes, and strategic partnerships that would **create a strong foundation for creating impact across the lifetime of the SKA.**

Reflecting on the discussions, the impact activities will focus on three types of activity:

- Building strong foundations
- Quick wins
- Lowering the barrier for the community

UKSRC Social & Economic Impact Focus Group - Industry and Knowledge Exchange 23rd June 2022 9:30 – 12:30

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This focus group built on the discussions with the UK astronomy community in workshop 1 which focused on Astronomy Science interests, demonstrators and engagement on 30 May 2022.

The aim of this focus group was to determine how we could develop knowledge exchange, co-creation and collaboration activities industry, other research fields and digital research infrastructures. The discussion points and suggestions are summarised below.

Co-creation & Collaboration breakout group

What works with engaging SME and industry in projects?

- Not too many partners, so you are not spread too thin developing collaboration
- ESSENTIAL: Two-way flow of benefits - what's in it for them (industry, SMEs), and spell this out
- Common interests in project, Projects of mutual interest, Common problems but not necessarily common outcome goals
- Mapping different roadmaps and goals (NEEDS time an EFFORT, and probably funding).
- Money flow not a deal breaker
- Good communications throughout re goals, projects
- Be realistic with planning.
- Focus on key partners. Don't over stretch.
- Process (set up early) for partnerships are managed (how many/scope)
- Develop good relationships, it takes time and effort
- Find out industry interests and capabilities and the fit to opportunities
- Enabling SME - consultancies to allow resources to be allocated

What works well building and growing an industry partner network?

- Industry/partner database/ CRM. E.g. could also advertise opps to STFC's industry database
- Events to highlight opportunities, promote networking, showcase achievements
- Need some clear plan/realistic about how many partners we can work with. How to do this is difficult How to prioritise partnerships? Overview of everything. If there are 10 agreed partners - what do we do when #11 approaches us
- Regular comms, e.g. newsletter
- Some funding that can be matched with industry investments helps - commitment (e.g. fund the person on the SKA side)
- Kudos for companies who take part

- Takes people effort and time to build relationships with partners. Time to understand where they are heading, where is SKA heading. And then mutual projects. Requires funding
- Projects of mutual interest
- Working across university support services well
- Sell benefits to industry
- Different cultures - industry/academia e.g. Timeline differences between industry and science. Timelines/ cycles of development
- Being a bit more formal in agreeing timelines, deliverables, keep people focused.

What works well in co-creation/ technology development projects with industry and SME partners?

- Sell benefits (develop knowledge of cutting edge R&D, skills, kudos re big science involvement)
- Clear motivation for each partner's involvement
- there is an opportunity for large companies to fund SMEs on R&D in collaboration
- SKA - Changing from exploring to creating a product (there is a lock-in).
- Look at roadmap to see if partnerships look suitable for 3-5 year horizon.
- Design activities between very specific with vendors vs vendor agnostic projects. Able to work in both
- Clear understanding of IP is dealt with (ownership and rights to use)
- seed fund for SMEs and how the results from Amy engagement can get reflected/ paid back

What other funding schemes should we be aware of?

- Business finance, grants and other forms of support for UK companies can be found on the BEIS website
- <https://www.gov.uk/business-finance-support>
- Wide variety of schemes, which can be searched on type of support, business stage, industry, number of employees and region
- UKRI funding, Innovate UK, STFC E.g. Knowledge Transfer Partnerships, IUK Smart Grants
- Eligibility criteria such as UK-registered companies, R&D must be carried out in UK

Knowledge exchange with other research fields, digital research infrastructures and industry

Which sectors face the similar technical challenges?

- AI/HPC integration
- Next Generation Archer/Dirac
- HPC systems
- Image processing technique / signal work
- The move to Edge

Which knowledge exchange approaches have worked well before?

- KTPs via UKRI
- Collaboration with vendor benchmarking / co-design for new tech
- Collaboration of model development / use (Deep Learning)
- Collaboration agreements, rather than individual NDAs
- DiRAC industry placements
- Post Doc projects and industry transition
- PhD / Early Career placements / RSEs

Which existing forums/ conferences/ groups could we join or present at?

- Consider what outcomes we want to see
- DRI Retreat and follow on activities
- STFC newsletter; emails to specific sectors (e.g. ICT)
- SC, ISC, CIUK
- A UKRI cross-council workshop for digital research infrastructures sharing technical developments be of interest

What are the training needs of the wider community that would be of interest?

- Best practice integrating AI into HPC workflow
- What is new / different ?
- See how industry approaches similar scale data challenges
- Domain specifics vs. tech solutions that could be transferable
- Cross council approach required
- How to comply with UKRI open data mandate

What works well when commercialising new algorithms, workflows and designs?

- Consider which outputs (not) to open source
- GPL lock in complicates direct commercial exploitation e.g. of Barcelona SC spinouts
- Consider SKA wide software licence?
- Identify IP ownership and agree NDAs/Collaboration agreements early. Open source.
- Access to and rights to use IP
- MIT license preferred, OSS required for SKA

Other comments

- One way flow of people, due to salary and career progression aspects. Limits to both in university type settings.
- People who gain experience and go into industry may not return...
- Loss of skills is a real problem.
- What would opportunities for “returners” look like?
- What would wider UK HPC community encompassing research and industry look like?

- Perceived permanency of role in industry is attractive to postdocs/RSEs. However not always born out in reality. Small number of senior returners e.g. Professors
- Career paths/progression for RSEs, data stewards, community engagement managers, project managers, and other research support staff will be included in the proposal
- UKRI/institutions could step up to give RSEs/RTPs confidence that their posts have continuity. REFable status for DRI professionals would help to establish their value (but would unis agree to underwrite positions?) e.g. have the RSEs sit in the local RSE/research software group with 100% of their time bought out for SRC work for the grant duration
- Industry/academia Centres of Excellence provide an opportunity for people to have a foot in both camp

UKSRC Social & Economic Impact Focus Group - Training and Professional Development

29 June 2022 14:00 – 16:30

Contributors: Wes Armour (University of Oxford), Alastair Basden (Durham University and STFC DiRAC), George Beckett (University of Edinburgh), Rob Beswick (University of Manchester), Andrew Blain (University of Leicester), Louise Chisholm (UCL), Iulia Cimpan (University of Manchester), Keith Grainge (University of Manchester), Martin Hamilton (UCL, SPF ExCALIBUR programme), Leah Morabito (Durham University), Bob Watson (University of Manchester), Marion Weinzierl (Durham University, N8 CIR), Mark Wilkinson (Director, STFC DiRAC and University of Leicester), Jeremy Yates (UCL)

This focus group built on the discussions with the UK astronomy community in workshop 1 which focused on Astronomy Science interests, demonstrators and engagement on 30 May 2022.

The aim of this focus group was to determine how we could incorporate training and professional development in the proposal. The attendees were asked to consider what training exists, who could we partner with, what should we lead in regarding training for astronomy researchers in big data and computational approaches; training in astronomy skills and training for digital research professionals (RSE/ ResOps/ Research Data etc). The discussion points and suggestions are summarised below.

Training for astronomy researchers in big data/ computational approaches

- Potential partners: DiRAC, LOFAR (in particular hires data), Software Sustainability Institute, IDIA (ilifu) training, SciML group at RAL
- Intro to SRC access course: Tutorials, Worked examples, You tube channel (with accredited!)
- Use of HPC facilities for SRC data processing (Intro to SRC computing) – probably need a new training course
- Training on SKA data products – what will be available and data sizes etc.
- Metadata tagging
- Automated verification of outputs
- Data management / efficient use of disk space for large data volumes - provide tools that work on stuff behind scenes
- Lead creation of a community of people with required data skills
- Mentoring to share knowledge of new techniques across the community and support translation of training into actual results
- Transferable skills will be highly prized outside SKA and perhaps we can develop a pipeline of people and then “accrete” a fraction of these into the SKA community.

Training in astronomy skills e.g. summer schools, interferometry

- Timescales to match with facility rollout
- Data science training for established astronomers
 - Mock data, Demonstration of benefits, Examples of mining paying off
- Audience?
 - Different
 - Demonstration of utilities

- Interferometer schools
 - Existing observatories
 - SKA program
- What do users want - quick-look speed vs detailed ability to hone and tune
- Credit and recognition

Tech Professionals'

- ResOps training: Data curation, System management, System efficiency, System monitoring, AI, K8S, containers, OpenStack, Networking, Management of, efficient use and configuration of Storage systems.
- SKA Dev Stack e.g. K8S, Docker, GitLab etc
- Existing training: Archer, DiRAC, Tier-2, OpenStack, Vendor-supplied (e.g. NVIDIA - basics), Excalibur: [UNIVERSE HPC](#), as well as the [Algorithms on HPC](#) grant.
- HPC Carpentry (slurm) www.hpc-uk.ac.uk
- Certificated training - helps RTPs career progression / recognition
- Training on how to use large systems efficiently and effectively
- SKA specifics e.g. Log Message Format
- RSE Society - mentoring programme <https://society-rse.org/events/pilot-mentoring-programme/>
- Openstack trained staff, Research Infrastructure Engineers
- Collaborations with UKSRC -SKAO in HPC, data etc
- Masters programmes, ATI Data Challenges Workshops, RAL Graduate Programme
- Experience of using pipelines - HPC in action. Data wranglers needed
- SKA could fund RSE Fellowships ?
- Hackathons, data study groups - <https://www.turing.ac.uk/collaborate-turing/data-study-groups>
- create feeder channel for new entrants HPC/RSEs. -Widen the net to undergraduates, Combine challenges with Career Pathways
- LSST Stack club - for those that use the pipeline Collaboration opportunity? <https://github.com/LSSTScienceCollaborations/StackClub>
- Working environment Career pathways for non-people management
- Difficult to compete with industry research, Issue with training staff that leaves to industry for better salaries
- Large-scale storage (HSM-like), distributed data management

UKSRC Social & Economic Impact Focus Group - Outreach and Public Engagement

24th June 2022 9:30 – 12:30

Contributors: Wes Armour (University of Oxford), Rob Beswick (University of Manchester), Andrew Blain (University of Leicester), Emma Chapman (University of Nottingham), Louise Chisholm (UCL), Alex Clarke (SKAO), Vasilis Kapsalis (SambaNova Systems), Hilary Kay (UK SKA Outreach Officer), Tim O'Brien (University of Manchester)

This focus group is part of a series of activities which aim to engage with the UK community to co-create the proposal for the STFC's funding call '[UK Square Kilometre Array \(SKA\) Regional Centre: 2022](#)'.

This focus group built on the discussions with the UK astronomy community in workshop 1 which focused on Astronomy Science interests, demonstrators and engagement on 30 May 2022. The aim of this focus group was to determine how we can incorporate public engagement and outreach activities in the proposal. In this focus group the attendees were asked to consider

1. How can we create opportunities for two-way interactions between the research community and society.
2. How can we inspire young people to value science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) skills and consider STEM careers.

The discussion points and suggestions are summarised below. It was noted that care is needed in prioritising and harnessing the interest and resources in radioastronomy and SKA project.

Opportunities to learn from or partner with engineering, astronomy groups and professional service teams

- SKAO/comms/public engagement team.
- With SKA headquarters in the UK, and media being strongly English-based, UK contribution could be magnified in the overall worldwide outreach impact
- Have SKAO partner with the discovery centre - staff can give talks for visiting groups (Tim - we already do this, but we could have visiting speakers via zoom as well!)
- Public engagement for engineering aspects of the project: PRACE, SUMMIT, ARCHER2, DiRAC, COMPBIOMED
- Partners with programme development to build and design telescope, science committee. Works with discovery centre, Jodrell Bank,
- What can we learn from ALMA & Webb? It's a similar scale projects
- Raspberry pi kits for students and coding projects. SETI at home computer model for home engagement? Night Sky explored app?
- Partner with university activities (which are probably quite extensive at all our unis - particularly WP schools etc), and professional institutions like IoP, RAE, and science centre network. STEM Ambassador programme in engineering firms etc.
- Think broader in terms of learned societies: Royal Society of Chemistry for exoplanet biochem; Royal Academy of Engineering; Royal Institute of Philosophy for SETI contact; Royal Academy of Arts
- "National Space Centre" here in Leicester has a wide network of school links and events, and don't just do in-space space. I'm sure they'd be interested.
- DARA big data skills in sub saharan Africa - material can be reused
- [NERC Data Trails](#) might be something to look at applying to SKA/ pathfinders
- Links to IAU-OAD, other international ORP..

- Is there a museum of radio astronomy? Link to association of science museum, planetariums, inflatable planetarium?
- How does UKSRC fit into other programmes internationally?

Develop and use networks to amplify outreach and public engagement activities

- SKAO/comms/PE. Raise awareness with adults of science & tech involved in SKA. Benefits to UK society. Articles in contact magazine, via STFC channels.
- Who are our academic PE outreach experts. Focus on the people and unexpected benefits of SKA discoveries/engineering. E.g. biro from space programme
- Audience and Channels. Social media! Podcasts
- UK Comms/outreach professional network - STFC, universities, Jodral Bank, SKAO
- Build connection with UK science with the UK community
- Have contact list of media savvy scientists in order to share news for wide reach and encourage on-brand discussion - without compromising independence
- Engage with some appropriately vetted "influencers", and provide content/contacts for them.
- PR teams from vendors to SKA?
- Access university professional service support
- Resource home is needed for the UK. Centralised Mailing list with trusted communicators
- University widening participation teams - network
- 3d printing models and sharing files for people to print their own
- Events; festivals, open days (need volunteers).
- Leverage academic spin out companies, where founders maintain research interest.

Training

- Media/social media training for scientists - make an army!
- Familiarise scientists with how to submit comments/articles to e.g. New Scientist I (EC) attended an excellent workshop on this which changed how I submit
- Hard to get media stories /blogs out of people. Need an astro background. Someone who can help identify and write stories

Develop a resource bank

- Resources and materials For PRs - then the community can use.. Need this - needs effort... Temporary exhibitions. Films/Planetarium style shows
- Do we have a standard up-to-date slide deck to draw from? Alex - there are up to date slides related to SKA background but you'll need to be, or ask, an SKAO employee to access them.
- STFC doing some videos! Build up material bank
- Roadmap of small steps/events/ launches to share with social media people. Share openly, with press offices
- Public data challenge data sets, and tooling for Jupyter notebooks image processing. Alex - this exists: <https://astronomers.skatelescope.org/ska-science-data-challenge-1/>
- International translations, but also locally relevant
- Provide outreach props! I made a 3D SKA antenna and it is amazing but it would be great for the office to have this kind of prop to share for presenters.
- Algorithm real Jupyter notebooks with data.

Work experience and internships

- Provide opportunities for work experience/internships related to SKAO
- SETI Internship programme with UG students, training for PhD. Looking for UK sites!!
- Working with internship programmes? In2Science?
- #10000 Black Intern program participation?

Material for teachers

- Reliable quality material for teachers networks - national curriculum compliant.
- Mentoring scheme in primary schools in Kenya - aim to extend uptake to high school
- Is there a way to introduce more advanced maths in a more simplified way for younger students for awareness.
- Topics in maths - visual elements. Enrichment sessions.
- Jodrell bank School programme links to national curriculum
- Connect to teachers and teacher training - they have far more interaction with school pupils than we could. Also national teacher training institutes for example.
- We should map the range of potential activities to the target audiences - what's good for a school group of 10 year olds is not good for 15 year olds, what's good for a generally interested (or even disinterested) member of the public is not the same as what's good for a very competent person working outside of academia but might be wanting to be involved at some point.
- Arecibo host general science fairs for kids... so they just get used to seeing a radio telescope

Topics for outreach and public engagement

- Try and insert radio astronomy into perception of astronomy - it isn't just optical! This will eventually increase desire for undergrads to study radio astronomy
- Hear about off shoots from radioastronomy e.g wifi
- History,(social history, war time history) of radio astronomy in UK. And the enabling technologies, and computing (Playing to strengths of radio astronomy - on earth. Human story.
- Playing to strengths of radio astronomy - on earth. Human story. Researcher journeys - how did you get here
- Highlight existing science from precursors/pathfinders - SKA might be added on at the end (2028 is a long time to wait for results. Highlight scientists and institutions involved
- In the long term, when data becomes available, having it easily explorable on a public website can be really important - take note from SDSS
- In the long term, when data becomes available, having it easily explorable on a public website can be really important - take note from SDSS
- Engage public with tangible data products to give context of whats happening. Simulated data: Whats coming next (SKA capabilities)
- Identify grand challenge problems in society than have analogous benefits for research
- Engage with large enterprise/national level that have analogous problems. Support skills.
- Awareness days - Women in STEM, coding week